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DYNAMIC CAPABILITIES IN TURBULENT ENVIRONMENTS: A PLS-SEM STUDY OF STRATEGIC AGILITY AND BUSINESS PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

SMEs contribute significantly to economic growth but often face difficulties in performance because of varying environmental conditions. Strategic agility helps firms reduce the adverse effects of environmental turbulence. This paper discusses the impact of strategic agility on business performance and the moderating role of environmental turbulence in this relationship. The study is based on the data of 408 SMEs in Pakistan, retrieved with stratified random sampling. It uses SmartPLS 4 for structural equation modeling. The results show that strategic agility has a positive effect on performance measured by financial, market, and non-financial indices. Nonetheless, this relationship is not moderated by environmental turbulence. The study questions the available theories of the moderating impact of environmental turbulence, especially in Pakistan, and emphasizes the significance of strategic decisions. The findings will assist SME owners, policymakers, and SMEDA on the improvement of strategic agility to ensure sustained growth and stability of the SMEs.

Keywords: Strategic Agility, Business Performance, Environmental Turbulence, SMEs.

1. Introduction

Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) play a major role in growing the global economy by creating jobs (Sinkovics et al., 2021; Zahoor et al., 2024). In Pakistan, SMEs are defined as separate businesses having employees up to 250, paid-up capital of less than or equal to 25 million PKR, and annual sales of less than 250 million PKR. These companies are important to Pakistan's economy because they aid in creating jobs, boosting GDP, and increasing exports (Iqbal & Piwovar-Sulej, 2023; Ullah et al., 2023). Therefore, leading to development and economic growth (Omar et al., 2024).

Despite their importance, Pakistani SMEs are not performing well. This declined performance may be attributed to environmental turbulence (ET), which makes it harder to survive during crises or heightened volatility (Caballero-Morales, 2021). This uncertainty is caused by globalization, increased competition, technological advancements, and varying consumer preferences (Taghizadeh et al., 2024). Smaller companies are more affected by the economic downturn than bigger ones (McKinsey, 2020). According to Oginni and Adesanya (2013), organizations are confronted with an environment that is becoming increasingly unpredictable, dynamic, and complex. This environment is characterized by the presence of many dynamic forces that have an influence on the overall performance of these organizations. The SME sector collapsing due to poor financial performance is a serious problem that could threaten the economy (OECD, 2020).

Business scholars and practitioners have a major interest in business performance (BP) due to its utmost relevance in the economy. Ongoing business pursuits create a persistent demand for targeted activities that enhance performance (Nurjaman, 2020). Evaluation and measurement of business performance is paramount both to the management and external parties that have an interest in the business (Aulová et al., 2019). Exploration and evaluation of business performance primarily aims to help a business implement strategies for improvement, ensure sustainability, and profitability in the long run (Melega et al., 2022). To be able to operate effectively in turbulent environments, a dynamic capability known as strategic agility is required (Idah, 2024). The propensity of a firm to operate in a varying environment by adjusting itself promptly

is called strategic agility (SA). It is basically the capability of the firm to react proactively and effectively to projected and current trends and activities concerning business (Poi & Sorbarikor, 2022). Survival of a business is no longer assured by mere financial resources or capital, but rather by adapting to environmental changes and devising strategies to maintain relevance. The survival of the fittest is no longer applicable to the businesses because the businesses possessing the ability to adapt and having significant resilience survive the longest (Akhigbe & Onuoha, 2019). Strategic agility is considered an important attribute for a business, particularly in turbulent times (Ahammad et al., 2021), as it helps firms to have better and enhanced business performance (Deshati, 2023).

There is insufficient research on the correlation between strategic agility and business performance (Pereira et al., 2021). Furthermore, there aren't many studies that look at how strategic agility impacts business performance in turbulent environments (Arici & Gok, 2023; Reed, 2021). Additionally, including non-financial performance indicators alongside financial performance could have provided an overarching view of firm performance in this context (Nurjaman et al., 2021). This research intends to advance strategic management's discipline by assessing the relationship between strategic agility and business performance, hence making a substantial contribution in the existing literature on environmental turbulence, business performance and strategic agility. Moreover, it seeks to rectify the shortcomings identified in previous literature. It also aims to investigate the moderating impact of environmental turbulence between strategic agility and business performance. In this study business performance is comprehensively analyzed by incorporation of two additional indicators: non-financial performance and market performance, alongside financial performance. The results of this study offer insights for owners, managers, and policymakers of SMEs.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Strategic Agility

The idea of strategic agility was first studied and applied in the manufacturing sector (Reed, 2021; Roth, 1996). Later, this concept made its appearance in information technology, supply chain management, and most recently in organizational structure (Harraf et al., 2015). Long, in his research (2000), examined strategic agility within the applied strategic management domain for the first time. According to him, strategic agility is the capability to briskly adapt to evolving situations and seize new opportunities while working towards a specific strategic goal. Doz and Kosonen (2008a, 2008b, 2010) and Doz (2020), argued that strategic agility encompasses three components: resource fluidity, strategic sensitivity, and leadership unity. The combination of these elements affects the degree of strategic agility that can increase business performance (Deshati, 2023).

2.2. Business Performance

Business performance is a complex phenomenon that has been studied in different settings. Improvement of business performance is acknowledged as the most important indicator of organizational health and effectiveness (Mushtaq et al., 2023). Different indicators have been used to assess business performance. Gunday et al. (2011), analyzed market, production, and financial performance. Tsai and Yang (2013), reviewed financial, global, and market performance. Other authors (Camisón & Villar-López, 2014; Shan et al., 2016), used market and financial performance. Kafetzopoulos et al. (2019) state that business performance refers to how good a firm's financial, market, and other non-

financial performances are. Financial performance refers to the efficiency of an organization regarding its finances, including profitability. The company's marketing initiatives, particularly those related to customer satisfaction and brand image, are evidenced by its market performance. Non-financial performance is an effectiveness and efficiency in goodwill and market reputation. The present study further builds on the same idea of business performance.

2.3. Environmental Turbulence

Companies have been very worried about turbulence in the last few years. The authors asserted that significant, rapid, or unforeseen environmental changes can yield disparate outcomes for businesses, leading to the success of some while others decline (Chatterjee et al., 2023). Turbulence gained prominence following the seminal research conducted by Kohli and Jaworski (1990), which identified turbulence as a significant exogenous factor influencing business performance. Environmental turbulence is characterized by circumstances encompassing heightened uncertainty and risk (Anggraini & Sudhartio, 2018). Moreover, Poi and Sorbarikor (2022) described environmental turbulence as complex, necessitating a flexible organizational structure for efficient and swift responses.

2.4. Strategic Agility and Business Performance

Ojha (2008) established that strategic agility has an adverse effect on business performance. Shin et al. (2015) found no effect of strategic agility on business performance. However, a comprehensive exploration of the strategic agility literature indicates that strategic agility positively correlates with business performance and significantly improves it (Al-Romeedy, 2019; Clauss et al., 2019; Kale et al., 2019; Kwon et al., 2018; Nzewi & Moneme, 2016). However, previous findings have been inconsistent, but the overarching evidence supports the notion that strategic agility is the key determinant of business performance.

Therefore, this study seeks to clarify this relationship and hypothesize that:

H1: Strategic agility significantly influences business performance.

2.5. Strategic Agility, Environmental Turbulence and Business Performance

Literature explains that the primary purpose of dynamic capabilities is focused on the moderating influence of the environment (Hernandez-Linares et al., 2021). A comprehensive analysis of the moderating effect of environmental turbulence shows that there is a negative moderating impact of environmental turbulence between strategic agility and business performance in oil and gas marketing companies of Lagos state (Arokodare, 2021). Turbulent environments mostly contain too many disruptions and uncertainties, which inhibit strategic agility from enhancing business performance efficiently (Wang et al., 2023). Research shows that strategic agility can result in increased business performance; however, significant environmental turbulence may limit its efficacy, resulting in complications in being responsive and adaptive (Clauss et al., 2019).

Based on the above argument, this study hypothesizes that:

H2: Environmental turbulence moderates the relationship between strategic agility and business performance in such a way that higher levels of environmental turbulence weaken the positive impact of strategic agility on business performance.

3. Theoretical Framework

This research is contingent on dynamic capability theory, which provides details about a firm's ability to adjust in an uncertain and fast-changing environment. Dynamic

capability concentrates on the examination of business resources and making them adapt to swift environmental changes using internal processes and resources (Teece et al., 1997). It is essential for businesses to quickly adjust to the dynamic business environment to improve their business performance. They should also capitalize on strategic agility for focusing on the reorganization of the company's internal processes and resources along with identifying new possibilities and risks in the market (Koay & Muthuveloo, 2021). Teoh, Lee, and Muthuveloo (2017) argue that even though strategic agility is vital to dynamic capability theory, the result is not always the same, as the functionality of strategic agility in amplifying business performance can be crippled by high levels of uncertainties and disruptions in environments. Resultantly, this study develops a theoretical model that integrates dynamic capability theory to explain how strategic agility interacts with the environmental turbulence to enhance business performance Figure 1.

Figure 1. Theoretical Research Model

4. Materials and Methods

4.1. Population

The study is based on SMEs situated in Pakistan. Among the private sector of Pakistan, around 90 percent consists of SMEs, which account for approximately 5.2 million active SMEs (Ahmad et al., 2021; Naveed et al., 2022; Jaworski & Kohli, 1993).

4.2. Sample Frame

The study utilises a sampling frame of 7,088 SMEs that were actively engaged with SMEDA for complaint registrations and effective communication, sourced from SMEDA's records. The researcher formally solicited assistance from the department due to the absence of downloadable or publicly accessible records of SMEs online. The Head of the Information Resource Centre enabled formal access to the database via direct communication. The Head supplied the dataset of SMEs that were actively engaged with SMEDA for complaint registrations and efficient communication. Therefore this research utilises a sampling frame of 7,088 SMEs.

4.3. Sample Size

This study used proportionate stratified random sampling, employing Pakistan's first

administrative divisions as strata to guarantee a representative sample. Pakistan's administrative divisions consist of the Islamabad Capital Territory and four provinces: Balochistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Sindh, and Punjab, (PCGN, 2023). The percentage of SMEs in these regions is 0.63% in Islamabad, 2.27% in Balochistan, 14.79% in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, 64.27% in Punjab, and 18.05% in Sindh (Competition Commission of Pakistan, 2023). The data was taken from 408 SMEs, which ensures accurate representation according to the given proportions (refer to Table 1).

Table 1: *Sample Distribution.*

Region	SME Distribution	Calculated Sample Size (408 SMEs)
Islamabad	0.63	3
Balochistan	2.27	10
Khyber Pakhtunkhwa	14.79	60
Punjab	64.27	263
Sindh	18.05	72
Total	100	408

*Note: SME distribution is presented in percentage.

4.4. Data Collection Instrument

The data was gathered through structured questionnaire. It is comprised of different measurement scales.

4.4.1. Measurement Scales

The contextually verified and highly recognized measurements scales were adopted for this research. All the variables were assessed by means of a five-point Likert scale inviting respondents to show their degree of agreement with each statement, from 1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree.

Business performance was measured using a 14-item Likert scale devised by Kafetzopoulos et al. (2019), whereas strategic agility was assessed by a 15-item Likert scale through Doz and Kosonen (2010). The study utilized a standard measure invented by Jaworski and Kohli (1993) to evaluate environmental turbulence, which at the beginning contained market turbulence, competitive intensity, and technological turbulence. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) found that market turbulence and technological turbulence had quite a high factor loading, i.e., over 0.7. Besides, competitive intensity appeared to be less than enough, signaling weak convergent validity, and resultantly it had been omitted.

This is in line with the recent empirical work, which found competitive intensity had no significant effect on SME innovativeness, underscoring the irrelevance of competitive intensity in certain contexts (Uzkurt et al., 2025). Moreover, researchers (Pratono & Mahmood, 2015) excluded competitive intensity due to its low statistical contribution in a study of Indonesian SMEs, because of its diminished role in comparison with other turbulence dimensions. In our Pakistani context, market turbulence and technological turbulence showed strong factor loadings and theoretical coherence, thus

justifying the exclusion of the third dimension, i.e., competitive intensity, in order to preserve contextual relevance and construct validity.

All the measurement scales were adopted from contextually verified, previously validated and well-established scales. Moreover, the analysis was conducted through Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) using SmartPLS 4. It includes built-in procedures to assess the construct validity and reliability, such as factor loadings, Cronbach’s alpha, composite reliability (CR), and average variance extracted (AVE). Therefore, the need for a separate pilot study was reduced.

4.4.2. Multi-Respondent Strategy

The questionnaire was sectioned into two segments and pertinent respondents were accordingly assigned. The responses of the first section, focusing on strategic agility and environmental turbulence, were collected from the company’s production manager, general manager, or owner of the company, whereas the second section about business performance was filled by the finance manager, CFO, general manager, or owner. The multiple respondent approach was employed to lessen the risk of common method bias; as a result, only people who really possessed knowledge of the relevant construct provided the answers.

4.4.3. Survey Distribution and Follow-Up

The questionnaire was disseminated to 850 SMEs initially through electronic mail. After 30 days, follow-up reminders were sent, and industry associations were contacted for their assistance in promoting participation. Even after these efforts, some of the businesses remained unresponsive. As a solution, the head of SMEDA’s information resource center was contacted to provide support. He facilitated collecting the remaining responses from the respective firms. As a result, complete responses from 408 SMEs were collected based on their respective proportions of the strata.

4.5. Data Analysis

Smart-PLS4 was utilized to analyze data It is considered as the key instrument in conducting Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) (Cheah et al., 2024).

4.6. Demographic Profile

Table 2 shows person-specific i.e. gender, birth-year and experience, as well as the firm-specific demographic variables such as the firm’s ownership, age and number of full-time employees. Out of 408 respondents, 87.3% were males while 12.7% females responded. Furthermore, 55.4% were born between the years 1981 – 1996, while those born between 1965 – 1980 accounted for 21.8% and the remaining 22.8% were born between 1997 – 2012. 25.7% respondents had less than 5 years of experience on their current job, 41.2% had 5 – 10 years of experience while 33.1% had more than 10 years of experience. Moreover, out of 408, 214 firms were sole proprietorship, 105 were partnership firms and 89 were the limited liability companies. The age of 41.2% firms was between 5 – 10 years, 30.1% had more than 10 years age, remaining 25.7% had the age less than 5 years. Majority of the SMEs, i.e. 66.7%, had less than 50 employees, 18.4% had between 50 and 150 employees while only 15% had more than 150 employees.

Table 2: Demographic Profile.

Attributes	Frequency	(%)	Mean	S.D
Gender			1.13	.334
Male	356	87.3%		

Attributes	Frequency	(%)	Mean	S.D
Female	52	12.7%		
Birth Year			2.01	.669
1965 - 1980	89	21.8%		
1981 - 1996	226	55.4%		
1997 - 2012	93	22.8%		
Experience on the Current Job			2.07	.764
Less than 5 years	105	25.7%		
Between 5 – 10 years	168	41.2%		
More than 10 years	135	33.1%		
Firm's Ownership			1.69	.806
Sole Proprietorship	214	52.5%		
Partnership	105	25.7%		
Limited Liability Company	89	21.8%		
Firm's Age			2.01	.768
Less than 5 years	117	28.7%		
Between 5 – 10 years	168	41.2%		
More than 10 years	123	30.1%		
No of Full Time Employees			1.48	.742
Less than 50	272	66.7%		
Between 50 and 150	75	18.4%		
More than 150	61	15.0%		

Note: SD = Standard deviation.

5. Results

5.1. Measurement Model

The initial step of employing PLS-SEM is assessing the measurement model. Assessment of measurement model includes validity and reliability analysis by comparing the obtained value with the threshold value. All constructs had factor loading values between the range of 0.618 to 0.836, significant at the 0.000 level, except for ET9, which was excluded from the analysis because of its relatively low loadings. The Cronbach's alpha (α) values for each construct surpassed the acceptable level of 0.70. The measurement model values including factor loadings, t-statistic values, C.R values and AVE values for all the constructs are presented (Table 3). The AVE values of all constructs, ranging from 0.502 to 0.611, exceeded the 0.5 threshold. Furthermore, all constructs had C.R values higher than the threshold value of 0.6, signifying a high degree of internal consistency within the measurement model (Table 3).

Table 3: Results of Measurement Model.

Constructs	Items	Factor Loadings	Alpha Values	AVE	C.R.	Constructs	Items	Factor Loadings	Alpha Values	AVE	C.R.	
BP	BP1	0.765	0.951	0.611	0.956	ET	ET6	0.689	0.929	0.502	0.938	
	BP2	0.835					ET7	0.706				
	BP3	0.751					ET8	0.730				
	BP4	0.767					ET9	Omitted				
	BP5	0.823					SA	SA1				0.716
	BP6	0.818					SA2	0.656				
	BP7	0.784					SA3	0.768				
	BP8	0.836					SA4	0.755				
	BP9	0.831					SA5	0.723				
	BP10	0.797					SA6	0.696				
	BP11	0.780					SA7	0.706				
	BP12	0.704					SA8	0.713				
	BP13	0.723					SA9	0.765				
	BP14	0.712					SA10	0.763				
ET	ET1	0.728	0.862	0.509	0.892	SA	SA11	0.721				
	ET2	0.750					SA12	0.672				
	ET3	0.722					SA13	0.618				
	ET4	0.702					SA14	0.669				
	ET5	0.675					SA15	0.669				

5.2. Discriminant Validity

The issue of multicollinearity is assessed through the discriminant validity of the constructs (Table 4). The assessment of the discriminant validity of the components was conducted through the heterotrait–monotrait ratio (HTMT) criterion (Henseler et al., 2015). Table 4 demonstrates that all values fall below the least accepted value of 0.90.

Table 4: Discriminant Validity of Constructs

Constructs	HTMT
ET <-> BP	0.701
SA <-> BP	0.811
SA <-> ET	0.853

Note: HTMT = Hetrotrait-monotrait ratio

5.3. R² Coefficient of Determination

The coefficient of determination (R²) in the measurement model indicates that 59.9% of the complete variance in business performance is due to predictor variables.

5.4. Structural Model Evaluation

After scrutinizing the validity and reliability of the measurement model, the next step in PLS-SEM is to check the structural model [60]. The researchers first looked at the direct effects by testing the idea that SA predicts BP. Table 5 shows a strong positive relationship between SA and BP ($\beta=0.659$, $t=10.771$, $p=.000$). As a result, H1 was confirmed.

5.5. Moderation Analysis

The moderating effect of ET on the relationship between SA and BP was subsequently assessed. The addition of the interaction term ($ET \times SA$) showed that ET had a negative but not statistically significant effect on the relationship between SA and BP ($\beta = -0.020$, $t = 0.661$, $p = .509$). Consequently, H2 was not supported. This means that the change in ET does not change how SA and BP are related (Table 5).

Table 5: Path Coefficient Results

Hypotheses	Relationships	β Values	t Values	p Values	Decision
H1	SA \rightarrow BP	0.659	10.771	0.000	Supported
H2	SA \times ET \rightarrow BP	-0.020	0.661	0.509	Not Supported

6. Discussion

This research illustrates a significant positive impact of strategic agility on the business performance of Pakistani SMEs. The findings are consistent with prior research emphasizing the similar impact of strategic agility in enhancing business performance. A study by Orojloo, Feizi, and Najafabadi (2016) showed strategic agility greatly boosting the performance of banks in Iran. Furthermore, a comparative analysis of enterprises in emerging and developing markets confirmed an important role of strategic agility in enhancing business performance in both settings (Vrontis et al., 2022). Moreover, strategic agility is directly proportional to business performance in electrical and electronic manufacturing firms in Malaysia (Muthuveloo & Koay, 2023).

The previous literature acknowledged both beneficial and detrimental moderating roles of environmental turbulence in the correlation between strategic agility and business performance. The absence of a moderating effect indicates a divergence from previous studies. Al-Romeedy (2019) showed that those electronic companies which were agile adapted to changing environments better. Anggraini and Sudhartio (2018) investigated Indonesian banking institutions and found that market and technological turbulence positively influenced the relationship between strategic agility and business performance. Conversely, Arokodare and Asikhia (2020) found that high environmental turbulence negatively affected the agility-performance relationship in Nigerian oil and gas marketing companies. Reed (2021) discovered that in small manufacturing firms in Florida, USA, considerable environmental turbulence diminished the benefits of agility. Recent research suggests that the influence of strategic agility on business performance may not always be advantageous in turbulent environments (Sarwar & Rehman, 2024).

Even though strategic agility is important for driving business performance in SMEs but the lack of moderation of environment turbulence in agility-performance relationship necessitates an investigation into the underlying causes of these findings within the context of Pakistan. It might be due to the contextual factors. For instance, SMEs of Pakistan have to deal with economic volatility, political uncertainty, and changes in regulations and/or policies constantly, due to which SMEs have become immune by developing resilience and survival tactics thus making environmental turbulence a less destructive factor in Pakistan. Sarwar and Rehman (2024) state that inflation, devaluation of the currency, and the frequently changing government policies are the enduring problems that will not leave away any time soon. Therefore, majority of the Pakistani SMEs have forestalled resilience to economic uncertainty due its persistent nature. The firms have also gained the capacity to predict these challenges and to build up adaptive strategies to curb the negative impacts of environmental turbulence.

From the theoretical perspective, dynamic capability theory can explain the non-significant moderating effect of environmental turbulence on the relationship between strategic agility and business performance. The dynamic capabilities, i.e. strategic agility, enable firms to reconfigure the internal competencies as a response to external variations, often diminishing the direct impact of environmental conditions when such dynamic capabilities are strong (Wang et al., 2023). Moreover, in a persistently unstable or highly volatile contexts like, Pakistan, SMEs may develop routinized adaptive mechanisms. As a result, strategic agility functions as a self-sufficient dynamic capability resulting in enhanced performance regardless of environmental turbulence. This implies that firms get buffered from external turbulence as strategic agility gets institutionalized within the firm (Teece, 2007).

Furthermore, moderating impact of environmental turbulence also gets minimized when the environment is characterized by chronic turbulence rather than episodic shocks because such firms tend to normalize instability and integrate it into their operational logic (Wilden et al., 2013; Dunning & Lundan, 2010). In such cases, strategic agility becomes a default operating mode and doesn't rely on the intensity of environmental turbulence to drive performance. Therefore, the absence of moderation may not indicate the irrelevance of turbulence rather it signals a matured internalization of agile practices within SMEs against persistent environmental turbulence. In addition, SMEs in Pakistan often use informal market structures that are flexible and can quickly adapt to changes in the market. Business owners keep their operations stable even in the presence of unstable environment by relying on informal agreements and close personal relationships (Shaukat et al., 2024).

These results showed consistency with the main points of Dynamic Capability Theory (DCT), which states that businesses must develop certain capabilities which enable them to proactively detect, acquire, and reorganize resources for enhancing performance in uncertain situations (Teece et al., 1997). An important dynamic capability is strategic agility which not only let the businesses react to changes but also foresee those changes and come up with innovative ideas to tackle them. This improves the performance of Pakistani SMEs greatly. In this context, strategic agility in Pakistani SMEs enables businesses function efficiently amidst environmental turbulence, thereby highlighting the negligible or no moderating impact of environmental turbulence. Arokodare and Asikhia (2020) argued that agility becomes a mode of operation rather than a reactive mechanism when dynamic capabilities are fully institutionalized, leading firms to rely less on fluctuating environmental signals for adaptation.

Additionally, in contexts characterized by persistent turbulence, such as regulatory or economic uncertainty in Pakistan, SMEs may not perceive environmental changes as unusual or disruptive. Strategic agility evolves into an intrinsic capability that enhances business performance irrespective of external fluctuations. It underscores that dynamic capabilities are not solely dependent on the environment but can also shape the perception and management of that environment (Teece, 2007; Dunning & Lundan, 2010). This research advances Dynamic Capabilities Theory by demonstrating that in SMEs in emerging markets, dynamic capabilities like strategic agility can exceed firm-level adaptation strategies, even in the absence of explicit environmental factors.

7. Conclusions

This study significantly advances existing knowledge by empirically confirming the

positive influence of strategic agility on the business performance of Pakistani SMEs. Moreover, it contradicts the role of environmental turbulence in the moderation of the agility-performance link. This study finds no moderating role of environmental turbulence leading to the conclusion strategic agility remains the key factor leading to enhanced performance even in uncertain and turbulent situations. Using dynamic capability theory, the findings in the paper provide an enhanced understanding of generating business performance of Pakistani SMEs by proactive adaptation rather than reactive turbulence management.

7.1. Practical Implications

For practitioners, mainly SME owners and policymakers, this study highlights the necessity of the development of strategic agility through digital adaptability, agile decision-making structures and investments in managerial competencies. Besides, policymakers can also design an assistance program for SMEs that can help them strengthen their strategic agility despite external turbulence.

7.2. Theoretical Implications

Theoretically, it adds to the discussion on the strategic agility by showing that agility, when embedded in a company's structural flexibility and adaptive capabilities, can drive business performance independently regardless of the external volatility.

7.3. Future Recommendations

The study suggests that environmental turbulence may employ more complex or unpredictable influences on strategic agility and business performance than previously understood. This research suggests future industry-specific studies because industry factors affect this relationship. Klimek et al. (2019) analyzed 56 industrial sectors across 43 countries from 2000 to 2014, revealing that susceptibility to economic shocks differs by sector, country, and time period. So, environmental turbulence has different effects on the relationship between agility and performance in different industries and areas. This study suggests that future research should investigate this correlation across different sectors, industries, and geographical areas to improve understanding of the variables.

One of the potential prospects of future research may be to examine whether the absence of moderation of environmental turbulence between strategic agility and business performance is a development peculiar to Pakistan or whether the same trend is evident in other developing nations. A comparative analysis of SMEs in Pakistan and in other emerging economies would provide useful information on the role that environmental turbulence plays in the association between strategic agility and business performance in various settings. The study would be able to consider the influence of local economic environment, the institutional environment and cultural environment in the effect of environmental turbulence, which would assist in better understanding the challenges of SMEs in the emerging economies.

Future researchers are encouraged to explore more moderators, like the organizational culture, adaptability of leadership, and competencies of digital transformation, to further understand the processes that contribute to the SME performance in turbulent environment. Organizational culture is critical in determining how a business reacts to the external threats and a culture that fosters innovation and flexibilities may help in increasing the adaptability of an SME to turbulent environments. Another crucial aspect is leadership adaptability because leaders who can swiftly modify strategy to conditions can potentially enhance broad resilience and performance of SMEs.

Moreover, the rising significance of digital transformation in the contemporary business environment may indicate that the capacity of SMEs to digitize significantly may help them to evade the turbulence of the environment. Exploring these moderators might give a more holistic picture of the interaction of the various internal drivers with the environmental turbulence to influence business performance, which can be of useful knowledge to both practitioners and policy makers in their effort to facilitate the success of SMEs in the dynamic market environment.

Abbreviations

SMEs: Small and medium enterprises

SA: Strategic agility

BP: Business performance

ET: Environmental turbulence

SMEDA: Small and medium enterprises development authority

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Data Availability Statement

The data is available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Informed Consent Declaration

Informed consent has been obtained from all participants, ensuring their understanding of the study's purpose and procedures.

Use of AI Technology Declaration

The article was prepared with the help of Paperpal to improve the paper language, correct grammatical errors. ChatGPT has been used to enhance sentence structure.

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